

D2.3

Summary report on landscape mapping and ENVRI community meetings

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Deliverable abstract

The landscape of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in Europe is broad, and the landscape is also constantly evolving as new projects are starting, many of them aiming to become RIs in the long run. Despite the heterogeneous nature of RIs, in Europe the ENVRI community gathers the Environmental Research Infrastructures, projects, networks and other diverse stakeholders together to discuss the RI matters from the environmental perspective.

This deliverable provides a summary of the work done in the ENVRI-FAIR project task T2.2 ENVRI Community building and engagement. Firstly, the results of the mapping of the current Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape are summarised, and secondly the organised events for engaging and informing the community are described.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D2.3 - Summary report on landscape mapping and ENVRI community meetings

1 Introduction

The landscape of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in Europe is broad, and the landscape is also constantly evolving as new projects are starting, many of them aiming to become RIs in the long run. The landscape is also very broad in terms of defining what kind of organisation is an RI. ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, uses the following definition by the European Union¹:

“RI are facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation.”

ESFRI publishes a European Roadmap for research infrastructures regularly, and the most recent Roadmap was published in 2021². This Roadmap presents the European Research Infrastructures as 41 ESFRI landmarks and 22 ESFRI projects in six scientific domains. The ESFRI Projects are RIs in the preparation phase, and they have been added to the roadmap because of their strategic importance and to support their efforts in reaching the implementation phase. The ESFRI Landmarks are RIs which have already reached an advanced implementation stage and represent major elements and competences of the European Research Area (ERA).

The definition of an RI has also been explored in the RISCAGE project and in the summary report of the project³. There it was concluded that finding a working definition for an RI is often quite challenging, because the use of the term varies greatly in the international context, but also within Europe. However, a couple of common features were found when exploring the RI definitions in the international and European context. RIs were often mentioned to be used for the purposes of research or science, and their character was mostly described with words such as facilities, resources or services to emphasise the services they offer instead of concentrating in their organisational status. Commonly, RIs were found to be categorised as either single-sited, distributed or virtual RIs, and many RI definitions also mentioned examples of RIs along these categories. Finally, the RISCAGE report concluded that in many definitions some kind of instrumentation, collections or collaborative networks were mentioned, and included some kind of explanation of the unique or distinguishable nature of the RIs.

Despite the heterogenous nature of RIs, in Europe the ENVRI community gathers the Environmental Research Infrastructures, projects, networks and other diverse stakeholders together to discuss the RI matters from the environmental perspective. The ENVRI community is overseen and strategically led by the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures (BEERi). The current ENVRI-FAIR project has been in place to enhance the collaboration, communication and engagement of the environmental RIs and BEERi in the ENVRI cluster.

This deliverable provides a summary of the work done in the project task T2.2 ENVRI Community building and engagement. Firstly, the results of the mapping of the current Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape are summarised, and secondly the organised events for engaging and informing the community are described.

¹ Article 2 (6) of the Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of 11 December 2013: ‘Establishing Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)’

² The Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures – Roadmap 2021 (2021). ESFRI, available at <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/> (last accessed on 29/3/2023)

³ International Research Infrastructure Landscape 2019 - A European Perspective (2019). RISCAGE consortium, edited by Ari Asmi and Jostein Sundet. Available at <https://riscage.eu/riscage-report/> (last accessed on 06/03/2023)

2 Objectives

In the broad landscape of European Environmental Research Infrastructures new members of the community emerge as the landscape evolves, and thus not all environmental RIs participate directly in the ENVRI-FAIR project. Active and continuous mapping of the landscape for new projects and RIs leads to engaged and collaborative ENVRI community, where the more mature RIs can share the best practises to those newer organisations.

This task 2.2 of the project was designed to facilitate the dialogue between all the environmental RIs, also taking account those RIs which are not participating directly in the project. The objectives of this task were to support the ENVRI community building, cohesion and harmonisation of the Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape and to make sure that all emerging projects and RIs are informed of the opportunities and support available offered by the ENVRI community.

The actions of this task have focused on 1) mapping of the current Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape and 2) organising the ENVRI community meetings. The objective of the landscape mapping has been to identify and reach out to the new projects and networks in the environmental cluster, and the objectives of the community meetings have been to engage them with the ENVRI collaboration and facilitate the dialogue on their future needs and challenges.

Besides the emerging RIs, the community meetings also naturally have an objective to serve the current ENVRI community, taking account also those environmental RIs which are not in the ESFRI Roadmap or participating in BEERi. In addition, the community meetings support the wider objectives of the entire ENVRI-FAIR project in disseminating the project actions and results to a wider audience outside of the project beneficiaries.

3 Mapping of the current European Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape

3.1 Conducting the landscape mapping

The ENVRI-FAIR project has conducted a continuous mapping of the European Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape in this task T2.2. Mapping in the context of this task means searching and identifying the new, emerging and potential RIs or projects aiming to the establishment of RIs in the environmental cluster which would thematically fit and also benefit of the ENVRI collaboration.

The continuous mapping of the landscape has been conducted by actively engaging and communicating with the project consortia as well as BEERi. Several RIs are participating directly to the project as beneficiaries, and many others are represented via their host institutions. This has enabled an efficient identification of emerging projects and RIs and provided an opportunity to establish contacts and invite them in the ENVRI community meetings also organised in this task.

The communication within BEERi has been particularly useful in this task, as BEERi members include both RIs already in the ESFRI Roadmap, and also those not yet in or not aiming to join the Roadmap. The landscape mapping conducted in this task of the ENVRI-FAIR project has also supported the efforts of BEERi in compiling a more holistic picture of the current RIs and networks operating in the cluster of environmental research infrastructures.

3.2 Results and summary

As a result of the landscape mapping, in total 29 RIs, networks or projects were identified in the environmental Research Infrastructure landscape in Europe. Out of these 29, three RIs or projects (EIRENE, Euro GO-Ship and GROOM RI) entered in the ENVRI community during the project lifetime. Two new RIs, CETAF and GROOM RI, became the new members of BEERi during the project. In addition, EIRENE was accepted to the ESFRI Roadmap as a project in 2021. Euro GO-SHIP will likely become a member of BEERi in the future. GROOM RI was already presented in the ENVRI community meeting 2022. This all proves that the engagement with the ENVRI community has started actively.

The result of the landscape mapping is summarised in Table 1. The table lists the readiness level, ESFRI Roadmap status, ERIC status as well as the BEERi membership status of each mapped RI or project. The basic information and descriptions of the RIs mapped have also been collected during ENVRI-FAIR project, and they can be found in chapter 3.3 of this deliverable. The thematic overlap of each RI is also visualised in Figure 1 for atmospheric domain, in Figure 2 for ecosystem domain and Figure 3 for marine domain. Multi-domain RIs are included in all relevant figures.

Table 1. Summary of the conducted mapping of the European Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape.

New additions to the community	New addition to the community and the ESFRI Roadmap
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RI	Domain	Readiness level	On ESFRI Roadmap	Status on Roadmap	ERIC status	Member of BEERi
ACTRIS ERIC	Atmosphere	Implementation phase, Partially operational	X	landmark	X	X
AnaEE ERIC	Land, Water, Life, Air	partially operational	X	landmark	X	X
AQUACOSM	Multi-domain	Fully operational				X
ARISE	Atmosphere	Under construction				X
CETAF	Biological collections and taxonomy	Fully operational				X
DANUBIUS-RI	Multidomain (Hydrosphere, ocean, ecosystems, sediments)	Under construction	X	project		X
DiSSCo	Geo- and Bio-diversity, Natural History Collections, Environment, Research	Under construction	X	project		
EIRENE	Life sciences (environment & health, human exposome)	Under construction	X	project		
EISCAT_3D	Atmosphere	Fully operational (VHF, UHF, ESR); Under construction (EISCAT_3D)	X	landmark		X
eLTER	Critical zone	Under construction	X	project		X
EMBRC ERIC	Marine biology, ecology	Fully operational	X	landmark	X	X
EMPHASIS	Life sciences, environmental sciences	Implementation phase				X
EMSO ERIC	Marine research	partially operational	X	landmark	X	X
EPOS ERIC	Solid Earth Science	Partially operational	X	landmark	X	X

RI	Domain	Readiness level	On ESFRI Roadmap	Status on Roadmap	ERIC status	Member of BEERi
EUFAR	Atmosphere	Fully operational as AISBL				X
EURO-ARGO ERIC	Marine	Fully operational	X	landmark	X	X
EUROFLEETS	Multi-domain (Land, water, life, air)	Fully operational				X
EUROGOOS	multi-domain (atmosphere, ocean, ecosystem)	Operational				X
Euro GO-SHIP	Marine	In planning				
GROOM RI	Marine	Under construction				X
HEMERA	Atmosphere	Fully operational				X
IAGOS	Atmosphere	fully operational	X	landmark		X
ICOS ERIC	multi-domain (atmosphere, ocean, ecosystem)	fully operational	X	landmark	X	X
INTERACT	Terrestrial	Fully operational				X
IS-ENES3	Climate science	Fully operational				X
JERICO	Coastal	Fully Operational				X
LifeWatch ERIC	multi-domain (biodiversity & ecosystem functions)	fully operational	X	landmark	X	X
SEADATANET	Marine	Operational				X
SIOS	Multi-domain (Biosphere, geosphere, atmosphere, cryosphere, hydrosphere)	Fully operational				X

Figure 1. Thematic coverage of RIs in the ENVRI community from the atmospheric domain.

Figure 2. Thematic coverage of RIs in the ENVRI community from the ecosystem and biosphere domain.

Figure 3. Thematic coverage of RIs in the ENVRI community from the marine domain.

3.3 Descriptions of the RIs in the landscape

3.3.1 ACTRIS ERIC - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure

Status

ERIC

Domain

Atmosphere

Readiness level

Implementation phase, partially operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data services, access services, computational services, support service

Social Media

Twitter: @ACTRISRI

LinkedIn: @ACTRIS-RI

YouTube ACTRIS

Website: actris.eu

Understanding atmospheric processes predictions rely on complex models that are underpinned by observations. Without high-quality observation data to constrain predictive models, any forecast of the atmosphere is highly unreliable. ACTRIS produces high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres. ACTRIS provides services, including access to instrumented platforms and simulation chambers, tailored for scientific and technological usage for users from the public and private sectors.

3.3.2 AnaEE ERIC - Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems

Status

ERIC

Domains

Land, water, life, air

Readiness level

Partially operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Open-air and enclosed experimentation facilities on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, analytical facilities, data and modelling services

Social Media

Twitter: @AnaEE_EU

FB @anaeeri

Website: anaee.eu

AnaEE brings together a series of state-of-the-art experimental and analytical platforms for ecosystem research throughout Europe.

At the core of AnaEE's approach is a network of distributed experimental facilities, through which ecosystems can be exposed to a series of controlled conditions, from land-use change, pollution, biological invasions, rising atmospheric greenhouse gases concentrations, and to increasing extreme events such as droughts and heatwaves.

AnaEE also provides analytical services to support experimentation and offers access to models that can be used for the interpretation of experimental data, notably in conjunction with other sources of data, and also to assess the quality of the data.

The services are coordinated by the Central Hub with the support of 3 services centres: the Technology Centre, the Data and Modelling Centre and the Interface and Synthesis Centre.

3.3.3 AQUACOSM - EU network of mesocosms facilities for research on marine and freshwater ecosystems

Domains

Multi-domain

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Near-real-time data services, scientific training, transnational access to experimental facilities, joint research activities

Social Media

Twitter: @ aquacosm

Facebook: AquacosmEU

Website: aquacosm.eu

AQUACOSM-plus advances European mesocosm-based aquatic RIs by integrating the leading mesocosm infrastructures into a coherent, interdisciplinary, and interoperable network covering all ecoregions of Europe. It widens the user base by extending TA provision (> 13000 person-days), and strengthening the offered services, with 10 new partners, including an NGO and doubling of SMEs. We initiate actions to increase competence in mesocosm science in new EU member states (Hungary and Romania), and emphasize training of young scientists through summer schools covering various disciplines including effective science communication.

AQUACOSM-plus develops near-realtime Open Data flows and improved metadata, thus promoting Open Mesocosm Science in collaboration with leading EU-supported initiatives in the EOSC and fosters

wider sharing of information, knowledge, and technologies across fields and between academia, industry, and policy makers/advisers.

3.3.4 ARISE - Atmospheric Dynamics Research Infrastructure In Europe

Domain

Atmosphere

Readiness level

Under construction

RI type

Distributed

Services

Multi-instrument data service about atmospheric dynamics

Website: arise-project.eu

The ARISE project combines complementary observations for the first time - infrasound technology, lidars, radars, and satellites - with modelling, for a better description of the dynamics from the troposphere to the lower thermosphere, where routine high resolution observations are rare.

Data provides an optimized estimation of the evolving state of different atmospheric layers. The objective is to determine the effects of poorly resolved disturbances - such as sudden stratospheric warming events, gravity and planetary waves - on uncertainties in weather and climate models and infrasound simulations.

The expected benefits would be a better description of the atmosphere, an improved accuracy in short- and medium-range weather forecasts and remote natural hazard monitoring for societal applications.

3.3.5 CETAF – European Consortium of Taxonomic Facilities

Domain

Biological collections and taxonomy

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Biological and geological collections

Social Media

Twitter: [@eurotaxonomy](https://twitter.com/eurotaxonomy)

Facebook: [eurotaxonomy](https://www.facebook.com/eurotaxonomy)

Website: cetaf.org

CETAF is Europe's network of biological and geological collections. Collectively, CETAF is the leading European voice for taxonomy and systematic biology. Natural history museums, botanical gardens and biodiversity research centres from across Europe hold a wealth of biological and geological collections, including animals, plants, fungi, rocks and genetic resources. The collections of CETAF's 71 institutions comprise an estimated 1.5 billion specimens, including over 80% of the world's described species. To manage, study and open up these collections, our community brings together a vast array of expertise in scientific research, with over 5000 scientists in 22 countries. This unprecedented resource serves to drive scientific research and public engagement worldwide.

3.3.6 DANUBIUS-RI - The International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems

Domain

Multidomain (Hydrosphere, ocean, ecosystems, sediments)

Readiness level

Under construction

RI type

Distributed

Services

Physical, online and virtual access to data and services for observation, in situ measurements, analysis and modelling in River-Sea Systems

Social Media

Twitter 1: @DANUBIUS_RITwitter 2: @DANUBIUS_PP

LinkedIn: @danubius-ri

Facebook: @DANUBIUSRI

Website: danubius-ri.eu

DANUBIUS-RI aims to provide interdisciplinary expertise and integrated research infrastructure: remote and in-situ observation systems (including ships), experimental facilities, laboratories, modelling tools and resources for knowledge exchange along freshwater/seawater continua throughout Europe, from river source to sea.

DANUBIUS-RI will draw on existing research excellence across Europe, providing access to a range of European River-Sea Systems a ‘one-stop shop’ for knowledge exchange; access to harmonised data; and a platform for interdisciplinary research, inspiration, education and training.

DANUBIUS-RI’s Vision is to achieve healthy River-Sea Systems and advance their sustainable use, in order to live within the planet’s ecological limits by 2050.

3.3.7 DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

Domains

Geo- and biodiversity, natural history collections, environment, research

Readiness level

Under construction

RI type

Distributed

Services

European loans & visits system, collection digitisation dashboard, specimen data refinery, knowledge base, helpdesk, unified curation & annotation system, digital specimen repository

Social Media

Twitter: @DiSSCoEU

Website: discco.eu

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections is a new world-class Research Infrastructure (RI) for natural science collections. The DiSSCo RI works for the digital unification of all European natural science assets under common curation, access, policies and practices, and aims to ensure that the data is easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

As such, DiSSCo will transform a fragmented landscape of crucial natural science collections into an integrated knowledge base that provides interconnected hard evidence of the natural world.

DiSSCo represents the largest ever formal agreement between natural history museums, botanic gardens and collection-holding universities in the world.

3.3.8 EIRENE RI - Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure

Domain

Multi-domain (environment & health, human exposome)

Readiness level

Under construction

Services

Data services, access services

Website: eirene-ri.eu

The Research Infrastructure for EnvIRonmental Exposure assessmeNt in Europe (EIRENE RI) pioneers the first European Research Infrastructure on environmental determinants of human health, the Human

Exposome. EIRENE RI intends to support large-scale research for the interdisciplinary assessment of environmental determinants of health, including indoor and outdoor environment factors, lifestyle, socioeconomics, and the individual's ability to cope with various stressors such as infection or disease. EIRENE RI will provide harmonised workflows and integrated services for data and sample collection, as well as knowledge and tools that will be made accessible to academic researchers, private companies, public authorities and citizens through the EIRENE open-access system and the EIRENE knowledge hub.

The concept of a pan-European Infrastructure supporting research on the effects of long-term exposures to various types of stressors on population health and the roles these exposures play in the development of chronic diseases is based on ten-year experience of Czech national RECETOX RI. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2021, EIRENE RI already connects 50 research institutions from 17 countries.

3.3.9 EISCAT - European Incoherent Scatter Radar

Domain

Atmosphere

Readiness level

Fully operational (VHF, UHF, ESR) Under construction (EISCAT_3D)

RI type

Single sites

Services

Data services, access services, computational services, support services

Social Media

Twitter: @EISCATofficial

LinkedIn: eiscat-scientific-association

Facebook: @EISCAT

Website: eiscat.se

EISCAT is an international non-profit organisation, founded in 1976, conducting incoherent scatter radar (ISR) measurements in the Earth's polar upper atmosphere and providing data for the research community. EISCAT operates 3 ISR systems on 4 sites in Northern Scandinavia and Svalbard.

EISCAT_3D, a next-generation ISR system expected to be in operation in 2023 is under construction in the same area. The data the EISCAT provides include height profiles of electron density, electron and ion temperatures, and ionospheric drift velocities.

The primary design of the EISCAT systems is for investigating the coupling between the Earth's atmosphere and space, but they are also suitable for a wide range of other science targets including upper atmospheric dynamics and radio astronomy.

3.3.10 eLTER - Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone & Socio-Ecological Research

Domains

Critical zone

Readiness level

Under construction

RI type

Distributed and virtual

Services

Access services; Data Services

Social Media

Twitter: @eLTER_Europe LinkedIn: @eLTER

Youtube: @eLTER

FB: @eLTEREurope

Website: elter-ri.eu

eLTER facilitates high impact research and catalyses new insights about the compounded impacts of climate change, biodiversity loss, soil degradation, pollution, and unsustainable resource use in terrestrial, freshwater, and transitional water ecosystems.

eLTER provides researchers with access to over 500 sites and 50 larger LTSER Platforms across Europe and biogeographical regions, establishing and offering harmonised and standardised data, services and training useful to citizens and experts in their joint efforts to find sustainable solutions to the Grand Societal Challenges.

3.3.11 EMBRC ERIC - European Marine Biological Resource Centre

Status

ERIC

Domains

Marine biology, ecology

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Virtual, distributed

Services

Services for marine biology and ecology research

Social Media

Twitter: @EMBRC_EU

LinkedIn: @embrc

Website: embrc.eu

EMBRC is Europe's research infrastructure for marine biological resources and marine ecosystems. We provide access to wild-type macro and microorganisms, tools, methods and training for fundamental and applied research. EMBRC sites are spread across nine countries and provide access to ecosystems from the Norwegian Arctic to tropical Israel.

Our on-site laboratories and experimental set-ups cater to all types of research involving marine biological organisms, from gene expression and physiology to ecology and climate change impact, with support from our highly-experienced technicians.

EMBRC aims to advance the understanding of life in the oceans and sustainably harness its potential for the benefit of humankind in sectors such as health, biotechnology, and environmental monitoring.

3.3.12 EMPHASIS - European Infrastructure for Plant Phenotyping

Domains

Life sciences, environmental sciences

Readiness level

Implementation phase

RI type

Distributed

Services

Access to instrumented facilities, data and computational services, modelling, training, harmonisation, innovation

Social Media

Twitter: @EMPHASIS_EU

LinkedIn: @EMPHASIS

Facebook: @EMPHASIS.EU

Instagram @emphasis_eu

Website: emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu

EMPHASIS aims at improving food security and agricultural business in a changing climate. As the world's population is growing, we will have to significantly increase the yields of major crops. At the same time, climate change causes more droughts and extreme temperatures with negative effects on crop yields, further increasing the pressure to improve crop production. Plant phenotyping describes the

scientific exploration of plant performance with respect to structure, function, quality and interaction with the environment. It has become the bottleneck for the exploitation of crop genetic diversity.

The distributed research infrastructure EMPHASIS has been launched to tackle this bottleneck. EMPHASIS will provide access to instrumented facilities across Europe, develop tools for data management, novel technologies and knowledge sharing to enable scientists to better understand plant performance and translate this knowledge into application.

3.3.13 EMSO ERIC - The European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory

Status

ERIC

Domains

Marine research

Readiness level

Partially operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data services, access services, computational services, support service

Social Media

Twitter: @EMSOeu

Facebook: @emso.eu

Website: emso.eu

EMSO is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium that aims to gain a better understanding of the phenomena happening within and below the oceans and explain the critical role that these phenomena play in the broader Earth systems.

EMSO consists of a system of regional facilities placed at key sites around Europe, from North East to the Atlantic, through the Mediterranean and Black Sea, equipped with multiple sensors along the water column, in the deep sea and on the seafloor. These observatories constantly measure biogeochemical and physical parameters across temporal and spatial scales and support the transdisciplinary co-development of cutting-edge marine technologies.

EMSO advances the knowledge of ocean processes improving the resilience to climate change and natural and anthropogenic disasters. EMSO promotes sustainable blue growth in the marine sector through innovative services helping to preserve the marine ecosystem.

3.3.14 EPOS ERIC - European Plate Observing System

Status

ERIC

Domain

Solid Earth Science

Readiness level

Partially operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data services, access services, computational services, support service

Social Media

Twitter: @EPOSeu FB @EPOSeu

Youtube @EPOSeu

Website: epos-eu.org

EPOS, the European Plate Observing System, is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure that facilitates the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community in Europe.

EPOS brings together Earth scientists, national research infrastructures, ICT (Information & Communication Technology) experts, decision makers, and public to develop new concepts and tools for accurate, durable, and sustainable answers to societal questions concerning geo-hazards and those geodynamics phenomena (including geo-resources) relevant to the environment and human welfare.

3.3.15 EUFAR - European Facility for Airborne Research in Environmental and Geosciences

Domains

Atmosphere, land surface, biosphere, water

Readiness level

Fully operational as AISBL

RI type

Distributed

Services

Access services, data services, knowledge transfer

Social Media

Twitter: @EUFAR_science

Website: eufar.net

EUFAR is a multidisciplinary research infrastructure that links the operators of research aircraft and instrumentation with the broader scientific user community. Its objectives are to broaden access to the facilities and to the data provided by them and to promote collaboration amongst its members and user community.

EUFAR presently comprises of 13 member organisations in 9 countries. EUFAR facilities are typically deployed on observing campaigns of limited duration in the geographical location and time period that is appropriate the processes and phenomena of interest. Members support the user community with the preparation and deployment of facilities on these campaigns and with the subsequent provision of data. Measurement payloads generally comprise a mixture of instruments operated and maintained by the member flight facilities and separate user-supplied instruments.

3.3.16 EURO-ARGO ERIC - the European contribution to the Argo programme

Status

ERIC

Domain

Marine

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Float procurement, testing and deployment planning, at-sea monitoring, Argo data management and access, trainings for capacity building

Social Media

Twitter: @EuroArgoERIC

Website: euro-argo.eu

Euro-Argo ERIC sustains and optimises the European contribution to the international Argo program, providing, deploying and operating nearly 25% of the Argo floats network.

The ERIC is composed of 12 European countries that join their efforts to provide data both in real time for operational services (oceanography and weather forecast) and in delayed mode for climate and ocean health research, as well as ocean reanalysis and seasonal forecast.

The ERIC facilitates logistic-supporting monitoring at-sea, and has developed related services for its 12 members, from float procurement to data management and enhanced services for users.

3.3.17 Eurofleets - An alliance of European marine research infrastructures

Domains

Land, water, life, air

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Physical remote and virtual access to research vessels, instrumentation and large exchangeable equipment, data provision, education & training.

Social Media

Twitter: @eurofleets

Website: eurofleets.eu

EUROFLEETS is a distributed research infrastructure facilitating open free of charge (currently funded under the H2020 Programme) access to an integrated and advanced research vessel fleet, designed to meet the evolving and challenging needs of the Marine science user community.

Interdisciplinary research groups can access European, global seas and oceans to conduct excellent research, with priority given to new users, early stage researchers, women scientists and researchers from less equipped countries.

Eurofleets develops tools and equipment to meet the evolving challenges of marine research, especially for deep ocean research and exploration, data management, and virtual access. Free and open access to data is ensured, adding value, advancing knowledge and enabling further innovation. Additionally, training and exchange programmes for user communities and professional staff are provided.

3.3.18 EUROGOOS - European Global Ocean Observing System

Domains

Multi-domain (atmosphere, ocean, ecosystem)

Readiness level

Operational

RI type

Distributed, non-profit organisation

Services

Operational oceanographic services for marine research

Social Media

Twitter: @EuroGOOS

Website: eurogoos.eu

EuroGOOS is an International Non-Profit Association of governmental agencies and research organisations, established in 1994 within the context of the IOC's Global Ocean Observing System.

Today, EuroGOOS has 40 members from 19 European countries providing operational oceanographic services and carrying out marine research, coordinating six regional operational systems: the Arctic ROOS, BOOS (Baltic), NOOS (North-West Shelf), IBI-ROOS (Ireland-Biscay-Iberian area) and MONGOOS (Mediterranean): Strong regional cooperation enables the involvement of many more partners and countries. Through its ROOSes, working groups and networks of marine operational platforms, EuroGOOS delivers strategies, priorities and standards, towards an integrated European Ocean Observing System, to underpin sustainable blue growth. EuroGOOS activities feed into national and European strategies, enhance coordination and synergy at regional and European levels and promote European leadership in research infrastructures, science and technology.

3.3.19 EuroGO-SHIP: Developing a Research Infrastructure concept to support European hydrography

Domain

Marine

Readiness level

In planning, Horizon Europe -project

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data services

Social Media

Twitter: @EuroGO_SHIP

Euro GO-SHIP: developing a Research Infrastructure concept to support European hydrography is a project funded by the Horizon Europe programme. The project aims to set up a European GO-SHIP program to address the identified gaps in water column measurement programmes currently in place in the coastal European countries and doing so in the context of the European RI landscape. The proposed new services and access opportunities based on the network needs are:

- Shared facilities such as training, best practices, access to capability and access to equipment through a European Marine Equipment Pool (EMEP).
- Data curation to ensure fit for purpose data systems and metadata for both real-time and delayed mode quality-controlled data.
- Secondary quality control to increase consistency and add uncertainty estimates to observations.

These requirements will be compared to the set of services already available within the European RI Landscape and based on this a new structure for supporting European Hydrography proposed. Possible models range from complete service delivery within existing RIs and the establishment of no new structures through to the creation of an RI with a set of services unavailable elsewhere.

3.3.20 GROOM RI - Gliders for Research, Ocean Observations and Management: Infrastructure and Innovation

Domain

Marine

Readiness level

Under construction

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data Services, Access Services, Computational Services, Support Service

Social Media

Twitter: @Groom2RI

LinkedIn: @Groom-ii-ri

Website: groom-ri.eu

GROOM RI is a distributed European Research Infrastructure harnessing the advantages of Marine Autonomous Systems (MAS). MAS are highly capable platforms that can collect water column measurements at a wide range of spatio-temporal scales and, in recent years, they have become ubiquitous for marine research, Ocean Observing Systems and for industrial applications.

GROOM RI integrates national infrastructures for Marine Autonomous Systems and promotes a collaborative approach to collect and share oceanographic data. It provides access to platforms and services to the broadest range of scientific and industrial users, as well as other ocean observing RIs.

By maintaining a unique centralised provision of cyber-infrastructure, data and knowledge, it optimises the use of MAS in Europe to study climate and marine environments, and also supports operational services and the blue economy.

3.3.21 HEMERA - Integrated access to balloon-borne platforms for innovative research and technology

Domain

Atmosphere

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Provision of stratospheric balloon flights, provision of data from HEMERA and pre-HEMERA balloon flights

Social Media

Twitter: @HemeraH2020

Website: hemera-h2020.eu

HEMERA is a Research Infrastructure funded by the Horizon 2020 framework Programme of the European Union which integrates a large starting community in the field of tropospheric and stratospheric balloon-borne research, to make existing balloon facilities available to all scientific teams in the European Union, Canada and associated countries.

The complementary of the HEMERA members' capabilities in the field of balloon systems and operations will offer an easy and enhanced service to the scientific community.

A wide range of scientific and technical themes are addressed, such as astronomy, atmospheric physics and chemistry, climate research, fundamental physics, biology, space research and technology.

3.3.22 IAGOS - In-Service Aircraft for a Global Observing System

Domain

Atmosphere

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data provision, data services

Social Media

Twitter: @IAGOS_RI

LinkedIn: @IAGOS_RI

Youtube IAGOS_RI

Website: iagos.org

IAGOS is a European Research Infrastructure for global observations of atmospheric composition from commercial aircraft.

IAGOS combines the expertise of scientific institutions with the infrastructure of civil aviation to provide essential data on climate change and air quality. The objective of IAGOS is to provide the most complete set of high quality Essential Climate variables (ECV) over several decades. The observations are stored in the IAGOS data centre along with added-value products to facilitate the scientific interpretation of the data.

3.3.23 ICOS ERIC - Integrated Carbon Observation System

Status

ERIC

Domains

Multi-domain (atmosphere, ocean, ecosystem)

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data services, Computational Services and Support Services

Social Media

Twitter: @ICOS_RI

Instagram: @icosri

Youtube: @icosri

Website: icos-ri.eu

Solving the climate crisis and dealing with its consequences requires science-based knowledge. ICOS provides standardised and open greenhouse gas data from more than 170 measurement stations across 16 European countries. This open and high-quality data makes scientists' work easier, and faster and helps in providing reliable results. The in-situ measurements also provide an important verification for satellite measurements.

The ICOS stations observe greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere as well as carbon fluxes between the atmosphere, the land surface, and the oceans. The analysed, verified and quality-processed data from the stations is continuously published in the ICOS Carbon Portal. Besides thousands of data sets, it offers also scientific and educational products and services for the scientists and for a wider audience.

3.3.24 INTERACT - International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

Domain

Terrestrial

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Trans-national, remote and virtual access

Social Media

Twitter: @INTERACT66

Instagram: @eu_interact

Facebook: InteractArctic

Website: eu-interact.org

INTERACT is a network of 89 terrestrial research stations in the Arctic and adjacent high-alpine areas. It builds capacity for identifying, understanding, predicting and responding to diverse environmental changes throughout the wide environmental and land-use envelopes of the Arctic. Currently focusing on six societal challenges in the Arctic (extreme weather events, communication and transport, retrieving hidden data with AI, educating the new generation, emerging pollutants, increasing tourism).

INTERACT has provided funding for over 1,000 researchers to visit research stations through its transnational access, and in addition provides remote access whereby station staff makes observations and provides virtual access to data. INTERACT's Station Managers' Forum have provided several best practice handbooks about station management that are available on INTERACT's web site. INTERACT has also developed educational resources that have reached schools in over 50 countries, more than 200 universities and more than 15 000 users.

3.3.25 IS-ENES3 - Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling

Domains

multi-domain (atmosphere, ocean, ecosystem)

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Virtual, distributed

Services

Climate model data access and computational service, access to software

Social Media

Twitter: @ISENES_RI

Website: is.enes.org

IS-ENES3 gathers the community developing and using climate models of the Earth system and their data, with the key objectives to better understand and predict climate variability and change.

IS-ENES3 activities support the World Climate Research Program coordinated global and regional simulations and contribute to the standards for data and metadata required for WCRP's international repository. This community is a key player in the assessments of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and provides the multi-model climate projections on which EU mitigation and adaptation policies are built.

During its third phase, IS-ENES3 aims at pursuing the integration of the Earth's climate system modelling community, fostering the common development of models and tools and the efficient use of HPC, as well as supporting the exploitation of model data by the Earth system science community, the climate change impact community and the climate service community.

3.3.26 JERICO RI - Joint European Research Infrastructure network for Coastal Observatories

Domain

Coastal

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed, virtual

Social Media

Twitter: @JERICORI

Website: jerico-ri.eu

JERICO-RI is an integrated pan-European multidisciplinary and multi-platform research infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes.

It is seamlessly bridging existing continental, atmospheric and open ocean RIs, thus filling a key gap in the ESFRI landscape. JERICO-RI establishes the framework upon which coastal marine systems are observed, analysed, understood and forecasted.

JERICO-RI enables open-access to state-of-the-art and innovative facilities, resources, FAIR data and fit-for-purpose services, fostering international science collaboration.

3.3.27 LIFEWATCH ERIC - The e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research

Status

ERIC

Domains

Multi-domain (biodiversity & ecosystem functions)

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Data Services, ICT services, cloud services, web services, training

Social Media

Twitter: @LifeWatchERIC
Facebook: @ERICLifeWatch
LinkedIn: @LifeWatch ERIC
Website: lifewatch.eu

LifeWatch ERIC invests in three essential components: open access resources, reproducible analytics and mobilised communities. By equipping scientists with distributed computational and storage capacity, tools and web-services for data integration and interoperability, as well as with Virtual Research Environments, LifeWatch ERIC makes it possible to test scenarios of change in biodiversity, ecosystems and their services, and support the formulation of nature-based solutions.

Such evidence-based synthetic knowledge can then be made available to decision makers and citizens, empowering society to tackle planetary challenges and supporting the UN Sustainable Development Goals, the EU Green Deal and the 2030 Biodiversity Strategy targets. LifeWatch ERIC also provides training and learning opportunities for a range of users, ensuring access to all the data, services and resources available within the infrastructure.

3.3.28 SEADATANET - Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management

Domain

Marine

Readiness level

Operational

RI type

Virtual

Services

Data services

Social Media

Twitter: @seadatanet

Website: seadatanet.org

SeaDataNet - Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management - is a standardized system for managing the large and diverse data sets collected by the oceanographic fleets and the automatic observation systems. The SeaDataNet infrastructure links already 117 national oceanographic data centres and marine data centres from 35 countries riparian to all European seas.

The data centres manage large sets of marine and ocean data, originating from their own institutes and from other parties in their country, in a variety of data management systems and configurations. A major objective and challenge in SeaDataNet is to provide an integrated and harmonised overview and access to these data resources, using a distributed network approach. The networking of these professional data centres, in a unique virtual data management system provide integrated data sets of standardized quality on-line.

3.3.29 SIOS - Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System

Domains

multi-domain (Biosphere, geosphere, atmosphere, cryosphere, hydrosphere)

Readiness level

Fully operational

RI type

Distributed

Services

Science optimisation, remote sensing services, data services, computational services, access services, support services (e.g. webinars, training, logistical coordination)

Social Media

Twitter: @SIOS_KC

Instagram: @SIOS_KC

LinkedIn: @sios-svalbard

Facebook: SIOSKnowledgeCentre
Website: sios-svalbard.org

SIOS is a Norwegian initiated international multidisciplinary research infrastructure that develops and maintains a regional observation system for long-term measurements in and around the high-Arctic archipelago of Svalbard. Its central node is the SIOS Knowledge Centre in Longyearbyen.

The observing system and research facilities offered by SIOS build on the extensive observation capacity and distributed world-class research infrastructure already established in Svalbard by its members. This includes a substantial capability for utilising remote sensing resources to complement ground-based observations. SIOS focuses on processes and their interactions between all Earth system spheres. The core observational programme of SIOS provides the research community with systematic observations - sustained over time. To use the observing system more efficiently, SIOS offers a range of services and capacity building activities.

4 Open ENVRI community meetings

4.1 Community meeting 2020

The first meeting was organised in February 2020 during the first ENVRI week organised by ENVRI-FAIR in Dresden. The meeting was organised in two sessions.

(1) First session focused on “What ENVRI community and ENVRI-FAIR do, what do they offer to you (other RIs) and how you can get involved. The goal was to “inform them about the mission and expected outcomes of the ENVRI-FAIR project and ENVRI community collaboration, highlighting how they can benefit from the solutions and results that are being developed in the project and ENVRI community.”

(2) Second session focused on “the role of ENVRI community in the development of EOSC and how we can collaborate with the EOSC development groups and projects.” The goal was to discuss the synergies, potential collaboration, or (in case of other cluster projects), development of joint demonstrators, and last but not least, clarifying the position of ENVRI RIs in the environment of EOSC development projects.

The first ENVRI community meeting gathered about 40 people. The results of the meeting were shortly presented at the BEERi meeting next day, where many RIs not directly participating in the project were present.

4.2 Effect of COVID19 pandemic to the organisation of community meeting 2021

In the year 2021, the originally planned Open ENVRI community meeting was not organised because of the global COVID19 pandemic and travel restrictions in place at the time. It was concluded that these community meetings are only efficient if carried out face-to-face. Therefore, it was decided to postpone the organisation until ENVRI week 2022 and organise it as a hybrid meeting. This was seen to allow better engagement of the initiatives that are new to ENVRI.

4.3 Community meeting 2022

The community meeting of 2022 was organised as a virtual meeting on 3rd February 2022 on the 4th Day of the ENVRI week. In total 38 participants from several RIs attended the community meeting. In this community meeting a brief overview on the ENVRI-Hub, EGI services and highlights from three RIs were presented and discussed.

In the first presentation Rita Gomes gave a brief overview presentation on the ENVRI-Hub and also a live demonstration on the ENVRI-Hub in the current status. During the second presentation, Gergely Sipos presented the EGI services offered. The third part of the meeting consisted of three highlights from RIs: First Werner Kutsch (ICOS ERIC) presented the results of the evaluation of ICOS ERIC and experiences from the evaluation process itself e.g., reduction of KPIs. Secondly Laurent Mortier

presented an overview of GROOM RI, the newest member of the ENVRI community. Finally, Miguel Charcos presented JERICO CORE, an integrated pan-European multidisciplinary and multi-platform research e-infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes.

4.4 Final community meeting 2023

The final ENVRI community event was organised in connection with the ENVRI Week 2023, on the 2nd of February 2023. The session was organised on-site and gathered participants from approximately 15 RIs (Figure 4).

Figure 4. A group photo of the participants of the final ENVRI community meeting in February 2023. (Picture taken by Katri Ahlgren)

The session was future-oriented, collecting feedback from the community and gathering insights into the future. It was facilitated using so-called "Open Space" facilitation method, according to which people moved around in a room to discuss topics that were of interest in them. The discussion was summarised in the whiteboards placed in the room (Figures 5 and 6).

The topics discussed were:

- Q1: How have you (your RI) benefited from being part of the ENVRI community?
- Q2: What could be the ways for future cooperation without immediate cluster project funding?
- Q3: Vision for ENVRI: How could your RI benefit from the ENVRI Community in the future?
- Q4: How would you improve the ENVRI cooperation going forward?
- Q5: Some other topic not discussed here?

Figures 5. and 6. Photos highlighting examples of the whiteboards where the discussion was summarised during the final open ENVRI community meeting in February 2023.

The main results of the discussion were:

- Q1: Being part of the ENVRI community gives broader perspectives to each participating RI, and that makes sense as we are all part of the global climate system. It also gives the service developers more colleagues to talk to and share good practises.
- Q2: Ways for future cooperation without cluster funding could include scientific collaboration (writing articles together, and making sure RIs are engaged, not just individual scientists), organising Comms meetings and common training events, signing MoUs, advocating towards the European Commission, cooperation with data stewards, organising ENVRI meetings in scientific conferences and developing the ENVRI-hub.
- Q3: Benefits of the ENVRI community in the future include gathering more diverse data users (from other domains), visioning ENVRI as a “mediator” between RIs and EOSC, building common actions towards the member states (to join ERICs) and being an active participant in the ENVRI-hub.
- Q4: The ENVRI community cooperation could be improved by working towards a better catalogue of services via the ENVRI-hub and collectively working towards an updated landscape analysis for ESFRI.
- Q5: Other topics discussed raised questions on whether really a MoU needs to be signed just to enable RIs to work together, and who owns the ENVRI “brand” (for example in the context of proposals).

These results of the meeting will be used in planning the future projects and other ENVRI cooperation.

5 Conclusions

The collaboration with BEERi and organising the open ENVRI community meetings has proved to be a highly effective tool in identifying and reaching out to the emerging RIs, projects and networks in the European Environmental Research Infrastructure landscape. During the lifetime of the ENVRI-FAIR project, three new RIs or projects (EIRENE, Euro GO-Ship and GROOM RI) have been included in the ENVRI community. One of these have already become members of BEERi, one more will likely become a member in the future, and one was added as a project to the ESFRI Roadmap.

These results are highly significant, especially since the global COVID19 pandemic caused one community meeting to be postponed and another to be organised as a virtual meeting during the project lifetime. Therefore, the important work of the ENVRI community building and outreach efforts should be continued in the future.

From a broader perspective, BEERi and the ENVRI community have proven to be useful and valuable instances in organising and representing the environmental research infrastructure community. In the future it would be highly beneficial to continue the operations and close collaboration between BEERi and the ENVRI community. Organisation of the community can be very useful, if for instance new initiatives to gather all environmental data and services in one place in the national level emerge in Europe. The operations of BEERi and the ENVRI community also demonstrate the will and capabilities of cross-RI collaboration and common vision in the environmental cluster, and they can represent the entire community when securing new funding for expanding and improving the common services.